

Regeneration of anther-derived callus

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We tested four differentiation media for numbers of regenerates with green and multiple shoots from anther-derived callus. Nine indica varieties and five F₂ crosses of deep water rice were used.

Single calli cultured from each variety were inoculated with three to five replications of the differentiation media. Gamborg's basic medium with 4% sucrose and different kinds and concentrations of growth regulators was used to regenerate anther-derived callus.

D2 and D3 were best for green plant

regeneration (Table 1). However, D3 with adenine sulfate (AD) in addition to other growth regulators produced more multiple shoots. Adding naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) or benzylamino purine (BA) increased the number of green shoots. Degeneration of callus or dead tissue formation occurred in all media tested.

D3 was further tested with callus cultured from five F₂ crosses of deep water rice. Although it gave rise to albino shoots, the production of multiple shoots per callus was confirmed (Table 2). Single plants from the multiple shoots were grown into individual plants. The results indicate a varietal difference in regeneration ability and green shoot production. No single medium seems to be best for a wide range of genotypes. □

Table 2. Regeneration from anther-derived callus of 5 F₂ crosses of deep water rice in a specific medium.^a Gazipur, Bangladesh.

Variety	D3					
	g	a	r	mg	ma	d
IR43141 (BR525-2-1/ IR19672-155-2-11-3)	-	-	1	6	-	-
IR43126 (BR314-B-4-6/ DWCT 156-1-B-B)	1	-	1	3	-	-
IR43131 (BR311-B-5-4/ IR13429-299-2-1-3)	1	4	-	1	4	-
IR43615 (IR10110-23-1// BR222-B-249/RD19)	-	-	-	-	-	1
IR43841 (BR223-B-55- H2-B-RD19/BR576-331-1// IR11288-B-B-118-1)	-	-	-	-	-	1
Total	2	4	2	10	4	2

^a D3 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.5 BA + 5.0 AD + 1.0 K + 0.5 IAA. g = single green shoot, a = single albino shoot, r = root, mg = multiple green shoots callus, ma = multiple albino shoot, d = dead tissue, - = slight or no callus growth.

Table 1. Regeneration from anther-derived callus in 4 regeneration media.^a Gazipur, Bangladesh.

Variety	D0					D1					D2					D3							
	g	a	r	mg	ma	d	g	a	r	mg	ma	dg	a	r	mg	ma	dg	a	r	mg	ma	d	
BR9-HR7	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
CNM-20	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	3	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
BR601-3-3-4-2-2	-	-	1	-	-	5	-	2	1	-	4	3	-	1	-	3	-	-	1	-	-	-	4
IR29692-65-2-3	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
BR562-23-1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	4	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	1
IR13240-108-2-2-3	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	1	1	1	-	1	20	-
Delta	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cul 25315	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	2	1	3	2	-	1	-	1	4	-
Calrose	1	-	2	1	1	1	-1	p	2	-	11	1	-	lp	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	2
Total	1	0	7	1	1	14	0	5	6	-	22	13	3	4	4	3	2	9	2	1	3	5	20

^a D0 = Gamborg's (BS) + 4% sucrose, D1 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.5 K + 1.0 IAA, D2 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.25 NAA + 1.0 K + 0.25 IAA, and D3 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.5 BAP + 5.0 AD + 1.0 K + 0.5 IAA. g = single green shoot, a = single albino shoot, p = purple shoot, r = root, mg = multiple green shoot, ma = multiple albino shoot, d = dead tissue, - = only slight growth or no growth of callus.

Multiple reciprocal translocation from somatic cell culture in IR54

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We found a multiple chromosome reciprocal translocation (MRT), involving five nonhomologous chromosomes, from somatic cell culture of IR54. Young panicles were cultured in MS medium (sucrose 6%) with 1 mg 2,4-D and 1 mg

kinetin/liter. The callus was subcultured for one passage and transferred to MS medium (sucrose 3%) with 2 mg NAA and 2 mg kinetin/liter for regeneration.

One MRT plant was found in the regenerated plants. It was shorter than IR54 and its anther did not split during flowering. The pollen grains were almost empty and not stained by I-KI. No seeds were set under selfing; some seeds were set under crossing.

Chromosome behavior in meiosis of

pollen mother cells (PMC) was abnormal. Bivalents at diakinesis numbered 6 to 12. Only 5.7% of the cells had 12II at diakinesis. Various multivalent configurations were observed at diakinesis, such as tetravalents (10II + 1IV or 8II + 2IV or 6II + 3IV), hexavalents (9II + 1VI or 7II + 1IV + 1VI or 6II + 2VI), octavalents (8II + 1VIII or 6II + 1IV + 1VIII), and tervalents (7II + 1X) (see table). The tervalents were present either as a ring or as a chain (see